

THE IMPACT OF WORK PRESSURE, ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACT, EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION ON WORKING PERFORMANCE OF E-COMMERCE COMPANIES IN BEIJING CHINA

XINYUAN ZHANG ¹, CHAYANAN KERDPITAK ², YAMING ZHOU ³ and
NAPASSORN KERDPITAK ⁴

^{1,2,3} Suan Sunadha Rajabhat University, Thailand.

E-Mail: ¹s64584945009@ssru.ac.th, ²chayanan.ke@ssru.ac.th (*Corresponding Author),

³s64584950004@ssru.ac.th, ⁴napassorn.ke@ssru.ac.th

Abstract

The increasing development of the Internet has driven the development and growth of e-commerce, and more and more new generation knowledge workers have joined e-commerce companies. However, the fast work pace and high work pressure of e-commerce companies gradually affect the work performance of young employees. This study will introduce needs hierarchy theory, expectancy theory and social exchange theory in an attempt to explore the complex relationship between job stress, organizational commitment, psychological contract and satisfaction. By establishing a structural model with employee satisfaction as the intermediate variable, the impact of work pressure, organizational commitment and psychological contract on job performance is explored.

Keywords: Work Pressure; Organizational Commitment; Psychological Contract; Employee Satisfaction; Work Performance.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

The development of the Internet has provided a broad market space for Chinese e-commerce companies. Consumers can shop, pay, and transact anytime and anywhere, providing merchants with a broader market and more business opportunities (Deng, 2023). More and more people choose the e-commerce model to complete business activities. With its broad market prospects, flexible working methods, generous salaries and other advantages, e-commerce companies have become the ideal choice for many young people (Fu, 2023).

The new generation of employees has become the main force of e-commerce companies. They have a strong sense of innovation, have keen insights into emerging technologies and trends, are able to gain access to various business areas in a short period of time, and are willing to make more efforts to continuously improve their comprehensive capabilities.

Knowledge employees are the core competitiveness of e-commerce companies. Knowledge workers refer to people who master and use symbols and concepts to process knowledge or information (Cheng, 2022). Knowledge-based employees can continuously learn and master new technologies, use new technologies to improve the company's operational efficiency and

service quality, and improve the company's technological innovation capabilities, thereby enhancing the company's market competitiveness.

The e-commerce industry is highly competitive and has a heavy workload. Employees need to work overtime for long periods of time and often need to deal with emergencies. High work pressure has become a major problem faced by e-commerce practitioners. Through previous research, organizational commitment and psychological contract are increasingly important factors that affect employee work motivation.

1.2 Research Question

- 1) What factors affect work performance in work pressure, organizational commitment, and psychological contract?
- 2) How work pressure affects work performance?
- 3) How organizational commitment affects work performance?
- 4) How the psychological contract affects work performance?
- 5) How employee satisfaction mediates work pressure, organizational commitment, psychological contract, and work performance?

1.3 Research Objective

- 1) To investigate work pressure, organizational commitment, psychological contract, employee satisfaction and work performance
- 2) To investigate factors affecting on work performance of E-commerce companies in Beijing China.

1.4 Research hypothesis

- H1: The satisfaction of the new generation of knowledge workers is significantly positively related to their work performance.
- H2: There is a significant negative correlation between the work pressure of the new generation of knowledge workers and employee satisfaction.
- H3: Employee satisfaction mediates the relationship between job stress and job performance.
- H4: Organizational commitment is significantly and positively related to employee satisfaction.
- H5: Employee satisfaction mediates the relationship between organizational commitment and job performance.
- H6: Psychological contract is significantly positively related to employee satisfaction.
- H7: Employee satisfaction mediates the relationship between psychological contract and job performance.

1.5 Scope of the Research.

The research scope of this article is 100 e-commerce companies in Beijing. Each company issued 3 electronic questionnaires, totaling 300 questionnaires; managers of 15 companies were selected as subjects for in-depth interviews (Hain et al., 2006)

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Knowledge Workers

Knowledge-based employees have higher academic qualifications or rich work experience, master professional e-commerce knowledge and skills, and are good at analyzing the market. Trends, competitors and customer needs, so as to formulate effective market strategies and product planning for the enterprise, and have cross-department coordination and project management capabilities to ensure the smooth progress of the project and the achievement of goals. Characteristics of knowledge workers: (1) High personal qualities (2) Strong autonomy (3) High degree of innovation (4) Rich knowledge reserves (5) High degree of collaboration (6) Focus on personal growth (7) Concern about the work environment Demanding (Wang et al., 2022).

2.2 New generation employees

The new generation of employees refers to young people born after 1990. They have higher computer proficiency and higher technical ability; they have higher expectations for the future, higher requirements for salary income, desire for their jobs to become easier, and to have better control over their jobs time; hope that leaders will recognize and respect them (Wang et al., 2022).

2.3 Hierarchy of needs theory

Maslow divided human needs into five levels from low to high: physiological needs, safety needs, social needs, esteem needs and self-actualization needs. In terms of physiological needs: the new generation of employees generally have a higher standard of living and their basic living needs have been met. They pay more attention to the working environment, salary, welfare system, etc., seek stability and security in the workplace, value interactions with colleagues, friends and family, and hope to establish good interpersonal relationships in the workplace to gain a sense of belonging and support (Jin, 2019).

2.4 Expectation theory

Expectancy theory is a classic psychological theory proposed by North American psychologist and behavioral scientist Victor H. Vroom. Fromm used the expectation theory formula to express it as: $M=E \times V$. Among them, M is motivation intensity, E is expectation value, and V refers to the value of achievable goals that meet personal needs, reflecting the individual's emphasis and desire for a certain result (Jiang, 2018). According to the expectancy theory, when employees feel that their expectations are met, they will be more loyal to the organization, actively engage in work, and be willing to make greater contributions to the organization.

2.5 Social exchange theory

Social exchange theory (SET) was first proposed by American sociologist George Homans in the 1950s (Muldoonj et al., 2018). Social exchange relationships between individuals include not only the exchange of material items, but also the exchange of non-material items such as help, praise, and emotion (Liu., 2021). This article will use social exchange theory to demonstrate the relationship between psychological contract and employee satisfaction.

2.6 Working Performance

Astin (1964) believes that when an employee's behavior is conducive to the achievement of organizational goals, the rewards he or she receives from work can be called job performance (Qi et al., 2023). Based on the research results of previous scholars, this article divides job performance into task performance, relationship performance and learning performance (Wei., 2023).

2.7 Employee satisfaction

Hoppock formally proposed the concept of job satisfaction for the first time in his book "Job Satisfaction" published in 1935. He pointed out that the psychological and physical satisfaction that employees obtain at work is job satisfaction. Referring to previous research literature, this article selects work compensation, work environment and work itself as indicators that affect employee satisfaction.

2.8 Work pressure

"Stress is the body's non-specific response to any demand acting on it." This concept was proposed in the 1930s by Hans Selye, known as the "father of stress research." Employees in different industries and types of work have different stress sources and influencing factors. The Chinese e-commerce companies studied in this article, the industry and employees are facing tremendous pressure. Most of the staff are young and knowledgeable. Therefore, organization, environment, and individual were selected as influencing factors of work stress.

2.9 Organizational commitment

Although the academic community has not yet formed a unified definition of what organizational commitment is, judging from scholars' understanding of organizational commitment, the connotation of organizational commitment can be summarized from two perspectives: "behavior" and "attitude" (Li, 2023). This study classifies organizational commitment into three types: affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment.

2.10 Psychological Contract

In the 1960s, Argyris first proposed the concept of "psychological work contract" in "Understanding Organizational Behavior". The psychological contract is a contract of a special nature, which is a subjective feeling rather than responsibilities and obligations. There is no written or other legal form of confirmation and signature; there are mutual expectations between the organization and employees, and their content will change with the development

of the enterprise and changes in employee needs (Jiang, 2020). This study adopts transactional psychological contract, relational psychological contract and developmental psychological contract.

2.11 Relationships between Variables

Xie and Kuang (2020) conducted a study on the relationship between job stress and job satisfaction of higher vocational counselors. It is concluded that there is a generally significant negative correlation between work pressure and job satisfaction variables, that is, the greater the work pressure, the lower the job satisfaction. Cheng et al. (2022) studied the impact of teachers' organizational commitment on satisfaction based on the mediating role of burnout. It was concluded that teachers' organizational commitment has a significant overall impact on their job satisfaction. Song (2018) explored the relationship between the psychological contract and job satisfaction of young teachers in public security colleges. Research conclusion: The higher the psychological contract score of young teachers in public security colleges, the higher their job satisfaction. Liu et al. It is confirmed that the overall job satisfaction of manufacturing employees is significantly positively related to job performance, task performance and peripheral performance. That is, the higher the job satisfaction of company employees, the higher their job performance, task performance and peripheral performance (Liu et al., 2018).

2.12 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1: Conceptual framework

3. RESEARCH OF METHODOLOGY

This study conducted in-depth research in the following aspects through a combination of qualitative and quantitative analyses:

- 1) Identifying the components and influencing factors of work performance of new generation knowledge-based employees in E-commerce companies.
- 2) To study the relationship between work pressure, organizational commitment, psychological contract, employee satisfaction and work performance of new generation employees.
- 3) To analyze the mediating role of employee satisfaction between works pressure, organizational commitment, psychological contract and work performance.
- 4) To demonstrate the impact of employee satisfaction on the relationship between works pressure, organizational commitment, psychological contract and work performance.

3.1 Research methods

This study adopts a mixed research method that combines qualitative and quantitative methods, and uses content analysis method for qualitative analysis to obtain the intrinsic essence and characteristics of things; SPSS and AMOS statistical software are used, and analytical methods such as descriptive statistical analysis, linear analysis, and SEM are used. Conduct quantitative analysis and present the research results in numerical form to enhance the objectivity and accuracy of the research.

3.2 Sample sampling

In the quantitative survey, this study used simple random sampling to randomly select 100 e-commerce companies from 500 e-commerce companies (Qi et al., 2023). Each company randomly distributed 3 employee questionnaires, and a total of 300 questionnaires were eventually collected. The basic rule followed in this study is that the ratio of sample units to the number of parameters or quantifiable variables is 20:1, so the sample size of this article is $20 * 15 = 300$ (Hain et al., 2006). In the qualitative research, a random sampling method was used to select managers of 15 e-commerce companies from the 500 competitive e-commerce companies published in the 2022 annual report of JD Group for in-depth interviews.

3.3 Research Tools

In quantitative research, we mainly rely on domestic and international scales to measure variables (Li et al., 2021). The purpose of this article is to explore two research objectives. In a qualitative study, in-depth interviews were conducted with managers of 15 e-commerce companies. Through in-depth interviews, we determined whether the company managers' understanding of the five main variables involved in this study is accurate and sufficient, their views on the factors that affect the dependent variable of this study "job performance", and the relationship between these variables.

3.4 Data collection

This study uses questionnaires as the data collection method, and the research tools constructed are job performance measurement scale, employee satisfaction measurement scale, job stress measurement scale, organizational commitment measurement scale and psychological contract measurement scale. In the formal questionnaire survey process, this study mainly used simple random sampling and took advantage of the work to issue questionnaires by itself, which mainly included two forms: issuing questionnaires to respondents in person and issuing electronic questionnaires through the Internet. Finally, the statistical software SPSS 26.0 and AMOS software were used to summarize and analyze the data. In the qualitative analysis, in order to ensure the validity and rationality of the interview outline, this study first invited three company managers to review the interview outline, modify the interview outline based on their opinions, improve the content and rhetoric of the interview outline, and finally form Formal interview outline.

3.5 Data analysis

In the quantitative research, the reliability of the data was first analyzed, including reliability analysis and validity analysis. Reliability reflects the internal consistency and stability of the measurement results, and is tested and evaluated through the internal consistency coefficient (Cronbach's α) and comprehensive reliability coefficient (Li et al., 2022). Cronbach's alpha coefficient ranges from 0 to 1, and the closer it is to 1, the higher the reliability of the study; the composite reliability needs to be greater than or equal to 0.700 to be accepted.

Validity is a measure of whether a measurement tool or method accurately reflects the information that the designer wants to know. To assess content validity, we typically use the item-object consistency (IOC) test (Wei et al., 2023). This is a system where projects are scored by experts with relevant expertise. It can draw on the knowledge and experience of experts to conduct a detailed and comprehensive evaluation of each item of the measurement tool, thereby improving the accuracy and reliability of the evaluation.

Correlation analysis is to analyze the signs that there is indeed a correlation in the population, and its main body is to analyze the signs that there is a causal relationship in the population. The degree of correlation between two variables is expressed by the correlation coefficient r . The correlation coefficient r has a value between -1 and 1, and can be any value within this range. When there is a positive correlation, $0 < r < 1$, the scatter plot slopes upward, and when one variable increases, the other variable also increases; when there is a negative correlation, $-1 < r < 0$, the scatter plot slopes downward, so When one variable increases, the other variable decreases. The closer the absolute value of r is to 1, the stronger the correlation between the two variables; the closer the absolute value of r is to 0, the weaker the correlation between the two variables (Tang, 2018).

Descriptive statistics mainly focus on the basic aspects of the evaluation sample, such as the age, gender, rank, working years, number of employees, etc. of the new generation employees in this study. In this paper, we set five levels of employee satisfaction using a Likert-type rating scale: "very satisfied," "satisfied," "average," "dissatisfied" and "very dissatisfied." When

dealing with such problems, we need to analyze the frequency and proportion of each level. Standard deviation is a measure of the dispersion of data. The larger the value, the greater the dispersion of the data, and vice versa (Yu, 2023). The premise of confirmatory factor analysis is to have a relatively clear preset expression of the internal structure of individual constructs in the research model and the relationships between constructs, so that the sampled data can be compared with the hypothesized measurement model while eliminating measurement errors. Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a multivariate statistical analysis method used to build, estimate, and test causal relationship models. It reveals the complex relationships and interactions between variables by simultaneously considering the interrelationships between multiple independent variables and dependent variables, as well as the explanation of observed variables by latent variables (Tang, 2018).

4. DATA ANALYSIS & RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1 After passing the pre-survey, the formal basic information chart of the sample is as follows:

Table 1: Descriptive statistics (N=317)

	Demographic	Frequency	Percent
gender	Male	161	38.61%
	Female	256	61.39%
age	Under 22 years old (including 22 years old)	92	22.06%
	22-26 years old (including 26 years old)	122	29.26%
	26-30 years old (including 30 years old)	125	29.98%
	Over 30 years old	78	18.71%
education	Undergraduate	213	51.08%
	Master	112	26.86%
	Doctor Of Philosophy	51	12.23%
	Other	41	9.83%
Marital status	Single	222	53.24%
	Married	170	40.77%
	Divorce	20	4.80%
	Other	5	1.20%
Length of service	Under 3 years	214	51.32%
	4-5 years	94	22.54%
	5-9 years	80	19.18%
	More 9 years	29	6.95%

4.2 Data quality for each variable was analyzed using descriptive statistics, including percentage, frequency, minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis for each variable (as shown as table 2-6).

Table 2: Work Pressure

Variables	Mean	Remarks	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Min	Max
Individual	3.535	high	0.973	-0.138	-0.769	1.000	5.000
Environment	3.379	moderate	1.012	-0.184	-0.618	1.000	5.000
Organization	3.621	high	0.978	-0.358	-0.487	1.000	5.000
Work Pressure	3.502	high	0.785	-0.323	-0.507	1.400	5.000

Table 3: Psychological Contract

Variables	Mean	Remarks	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Min	Max
Transactional Psychological Contract	3.674	high	1.000	-0.442	-0.267	1.000	5.000
Relational Psychological Contract	3.480	moderate	1.024	-0.296	-0.509	1.000	5.000
Developmental Psychological Contract	3.530	high	1.038	-0.379	-0.361	1.000	5.000
Psychological Contract	3.560	high	0.799	-0.494	-0.227	1.133	5.000

Table 4: Organizational Commitment

Variables	Mean	Remarks	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Min	Max
Emotional Commitment	3.353	moderate	0.957	-0.111	-0.456	1.000	5.000
Continuance Commitment	3.739	high	0.921	-0.295	-0.566	1.000	5.000
Normative Commitment	3.444	moderate	0.979	-0.258	-0.497	1.000	5.000
Organizational Commitment	3.501	high	0.743	-0.227	-0.635	1.733	4.933

Table 5: Employee Satisfaction

Variables	Mean	Remarks	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Min	Max
Work Itself	3.602	high	0.995	-0.372	-0.449	1.000	5.000
Work Reward	3.357	moderate	0.973	-0.058	-0.566	1.000	5.000
Working Environment	3.559	high	0.926	-0.291	-0.223	1.000	5.000
Employee Satisfaction	3.491	moderate	0.767	-0.363	-0.302	1.200	4.933

Table 6: Working Performance

Variables	Mean	Remarks	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Min	Max
Task Performance	3.326	moderate	0.985	-0.160	-0.617	1.000	5.000
Relational Performance	3.470	moderate	0.951	-0.099	-0.573	1.000	5.000
Learning Performance	3.595	high	0.926	-0.243	-0.534	1.000	5.000
Working Performance	3.452	moderate	0.764	-0.191	-0.490	1.067	5.000

4.4 Reliability test of each variable of the research mode

Table 7: Reliability Analysis

	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Work Pressure	15	0.912
Individual	5	0.856
Environment	5	0.858
Organization	5	0.861
Organizational Commitment	15	0.908
Emotional Commitment	5	0.854
Continuance Commitment	5	0.855
Normative Commitment	5	0.846
Psychological Contract	15	0.913
Transactional Psychological Contract	5	0.864
Relational Psychological Contract	5	0.86
Developmental Psychological Contract	5	0.859
Employee Satisfaction	15	0.914
Work Itself	5	0.867

Work Reward	5	0.864
Working Environment	5	0.843
Working Performance	15	0.913
Task Performance	5	0.865
Relational Performance	5	0.856
Learning Performance	5	0.847

4.5 Confirmatory factor analysis results of Work Pressure, Organizational Commitment, Psychological Contract, Employee Satisfaction and Working Performance.

Figure 1: Multivariate confirmatory factor analysis model first order

Figure 2: Multivariate confirmatory factor analysis model second order

4.6 Path analysis and mediating effects

Table 8: path analysis

path			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Work Pressure	--->	Employee Satisfaction	-0.206	0.099	-2.076	0.038
Organizational Commitment	--->	Employee Satisfaction	0.278	0.105	2.64	0.008
Psychological Contract	--->	Employee Satisfaction	0.494	0.105	4.681	<0.001
Employee Satisfaction	--->	Working Performance	0.809	0.076	10.624	<0.001

Table 9: mediating effect analysis

Parameter	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P
Work Pressure→Employee Satisfaction→Working Performance	-0.166	-0.338	-0.005	0.044
Organizational Commitment→Employee Satisfaction→Working Performance	0.225	0.048	0.421	0.018
Psychological Contract→Employee Satisfaction→Working Performance	0.399	0.243	0.600	<0.001

Table 10: Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results

Number	Hypothesis	Result
H1	Work Pressure has a negative impact on Employee Satisfaction	Accept
H2	Organizational Commitment has a positive impact on Employee Satisfaction	Accept
H3	Psychological Contract has a positive impact on Employee Satisfaction	Accept
H4	Employee Satisfaction has a positive impact on Working Performance	Accept
H5	Employee Satisfaction acts as a mediator between Work Pressure and Working Performance	Accept
H6	Employee Satisfaction serves as a mediator between Organizational Commitment and Working Performance	Accept
H7	Employee Satisfaction acts as a mediator between Psychological Contract and Working Performance	Accept

5. RESULT SUMMARY

This research adopts a combination of questionnaire survey method and case interview method. In terms of quantitative analysis, correlation analysis and factor analysis were performed on the collected data. The study found that work pressure has a negative impact on employee satisfaction, organizational commitment has a positive impact on employee satisfaction, and psychological contract has a positive impact on employee satisfaction. Have a positive impact. Employee satisfaction has a positive impact on job performance.

Employee satisfaction mediates the relationship between job stress and job performance. Employee satisfaction mediates the relationship between organizational commitment and job performance. Employee satisfaction plays a mediating role between psychological contract and job performance. Interview analysis, based on quantitative analysis, deeply explores the depth and breadth of each variable, once again proving the hypothesis.

References

- 1) Chen, Y. (2020). Research on Business Model Innovation Management Based on E-commerce Environment [Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Harbin University of Science and Technology]. CNKI. <https://doi.org/10.27063/d.cnki.ghlgu.2020.000010>
- 2) Cheng, G., Dong, B. Y., & Jiang, Y. C. (2022). The Effect of Teachers' Organizational Commitment on Job Satisfaction - Based on the Mediating Role of Career Exhaustion. *Journal of Schooling Studies*, 19(5), 33–50.
- 3) Deng, C. (2023). E-commerce in modern economic management. *Trade Fair Economy*, (11), 63–66.
- 4) Fu, C. X., & Zhou, W. T. (2023). Research on Paths of Improving Employee Satisfactory Degree in Service Companies Based on SEM. *Journal of Changchun University*, 33(1), 8–16. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1009-3907.2023.01.002>
- 5) Jiang, C. H. (2020). Discussion on the Causes of Employee Turnover and the Coping Strategies from the Perspective of Psychological Contract. *Management & Technology of Sme*, (13), 112–113.
- 6) Jiang, L. (2018). Empirical Study on the Financing Performance of Crowdfunding Projects from the Perspective of Expectation Theory [Unpublished master's thesis, Tianjin University]. WangfangData. <https://d.wanfangdata.com.cn/thesis/ChJUaGVzaXNOZXdTmJyAyMzA5MDES CUQwMTkzNzA3NRoIdXg3eWI0a3A%3D>
- 7) Jin, X. L. (2019). Analyzing the Application of Hierarchy of Needs Theory in Human Resource Management Practices. *China Economist*, (8), 261–262. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1004-4914.2019.08.141>
- 8) Li, B. Y. (2023). Research on Human Resource Management of E-commerce Companies in the Era of Big Data. *China Circulation Economy*, (11), 101–104. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1009-5292.2023.11.025>
- 9) Li, H. J., & Guo, Y. Z. (2022). A study of the relationship between tour guides' psychological contract and professionalism in the context of atypical employment relationship: the moderating role of fairness sensitivity. *Mathematics in Practice and Theory*, 52(4), 1–11.
- 10) Li, S., Li, Q., & Yin, Z. J. (2021). A Study on the Relationship between Organizational Commitment and Work Engagement of Knowledge-based Employees in Small and Medium-sized Companies (SMEs). *Enterprise Science and Technology & Development*, (2), 166–168, 171. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1674-0688.2021.02.062>
- 11) Liu, F. C., & Xiao, L. M. (2018). A Study of the Relationship between Top Administrators' Satisfaction and Work performance. *West Leather*, 40(12), 110, 112. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1671-1602.2018.12.080>
- 12) Liu, X. (2021). A Study of Management Measures for Employee Organizational Commitment. *West Leather*, 43(8), 78–79.
- 13) Qi, S. S., & Wang, Y. R. (2023). Connotation, dimensions and influencing factors of work performance. *Marketing Management Review*, (8), 130–132.
- 14) Qi, S. S., & Wang, Y. R. (2023). Connotation, dimensions and influencing factors of work performance. *Marketing Management Review*, (8), 130–132.
- 15) Song, Y. (2018). A Study of Job Stress, Psychological Capital and Employee Advising Behavior. *Henan Social Sciences*, 26(9), 77–81.
- 16) Tang, Kimball. (2018). Research on the role mechanism of secondary school teachers' sense of organizational support on job satisfaction and job stress (Doctoral dissertation, Nanjing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics). <https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CDFDLAST2020&filename=1019633266.nh>

- 17) Wang, Y., Xie, Y., Zhao, X., Wu, K. Q., & Xu, S. (2022). A study on the impact of work pressure on job burnout among employees of e-commerce companies. *Hebei Qiye*, (5), 120–123.
- 18) Wang, Z., & Xu, K. Y. (2022). Corporate Social Work Intervention for Employee Burnout Intervention: An Analysis Based on Work performance. *Journal of Lingnan Normal University*, 43(5), 66–73.
- 19) Wei, C.P., Lin, W.J., Yang, K.H. & Zhou, W.J.. (2023). A study on content validity of documentary evidence retrieval from an evidence-based perspective. *Library Construction* (01), 44-52. doi:10.19764/j.cnki.tsgjs.20221817.
- 20) Wei, Y. Q. (2023). A Study of Employee Satisfaction in Media Group A's Integrated Media Center under the Background of Media Convergence. *Culture & Communication*, 12(3), 47–54.
- 21) Xie, S. W., & Guo, B. (2020). Research on the Influencing Factors of Employee Satisfaction in Local State-owned Small and Medium-sized Companies--Based on the Data Analysis of 15 Companies in Bazhong City. *China Small & Medium Companies*, (1), 135–136.
- 22) Yu, H. (2023). Jingdong business model discussion. *Old Brand Marketing*, (15), 185–187.